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1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) in NANOFACETS, the present Deliverable details all scientific publications from the Consortium from month 16 of the action. During this period the consortium published the total 11 peer-reviewed publications, 2 preprint publications and 11 conference papers. All publications have been deposited into an open repository, and links are provided below. The list of publications is also available from the project website: <https://www.nanofacts.net/publications/>

2. PEER-REVIEWED JOURNALS

The following papers have been published in international peer-reviewed journals (first page of the papers included in the Annex below):

1. Nekrasov, N.; Kudriavtseva, A.; Orlov, A.V.; Gadjanski, I.; Nikitin, P.I.; Bobrinetskiy, I.; Knežević, N.Ž. One-Step Photochemical Immobilization of Aptamer on Graphene for Label-Free Detection of NT-proBNP. *Biosensors* (2022), 12, 1071. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios12121071>

Abstract: A novel photochemical technological route for one-step functionalization of a graphene surface with an azide-modified DNA aptamer for biomarkers is developed. The methodology is demonstrated for the functionalization of a DNA aptamer for an N-terminal B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP) heart failure biomarker on the surface of a graphene channel within a system based on a liquid-gated graphene field effect transistor (GFET). The limit of detection (LOD) of the aptamer-functionalized sensor is 0.01 pg/mL with short response time (75 s) for clinically relevant concentrations of the cardiac biomarker, which could be of relevance for point-of-care (POC) applications. The novel methodology could be applicable for the development of different graphene-based biosensors for fast, stable, real-time, and highly sensitive detection of disease markers.

2. Knežević, N.Ž.; Ilić, N.; Kaluđerović, G.N. Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for pH-Responsive Delivery of Iridium Metallotherapeutics and Treatment of Glioblastoma Multiforme. *Inorganics* (2022), 10, 250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/inorganics10120250>

Abstract: Using nanoparticles for controlled drug delivery to cancer, in response to its weakly acidic environment, represents a promising approach toward increasing the effectiveness and reducing the adverse effects of cancer therapy. Hence, the aim of this study is to construct novel mesoporous silica nanoparticle (MSN)-based acidification-responsive drug delivery systems for targeted cancer therapy. Herein, the surface of MSN is covalently functionalized with Ir(III)-based complex through a pH-cleavable hydrazone-based linker and characterized by nitrogen sorption, SEM, FTIR, EDS, TGA, DSC, DLS, and zeta potential measurements. Enhanced release of Ir(III)-complexes is evidenced by UV/VIS spectroscopy at the weakly acidic environments (pH 5 and pH 6) in comparison to the release at physiological conditions. The in vitro toxicity of the prepared materials is tested on healthy MRC-5 cells while their potential for the efficient treatment of glioblastoma multiforme is demonstrated on the U251 cell line.

3. Erthal, L. C., Shi, Y., Sweeney, K. J., Gobbo, O. L., & Ruiz-Hernandez, E. Nanocomposite formulation for a sustained release of free drug and drug-loaded responsive nanoparticles: an approach for a local therapy of glioblastoma multiforme. *Scientific Reports* (2023), 13(1), 5094. <https://doi.org/10.1038%2Fs41598-023-32257-5>.

Abstract: Malignant gliomas are a type of primary brain tumour that originates in glial cells. Among them, glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is the most common and the most aggressive brain tumour in adults, classified as grade IV by the World Health Organization. The standard care for GBM, known as the Stupp protocol includes surgical resection followed by oral chemotherapy with temozolomide (TMZ). This treatment option provides a median survival prognosis of only 16–18 months to patients mainly due to tumour recurrence. Therefore, enhanced treatment options are urgently needed for this disease. Here we show the development, characterization, and in vitro and in vivo evaluation of a new composite material for local therapy of GBM post-surgery. We developed responsive nanoparticles that were loaded with paclitaxel (PTX), and that showed penetration in 3D spheroids and cell internalization. These nanoparticles were found to be cytotoxic in 2D (U-87 cells) and 3D (U-87 spheroids) models of GBM. The incorporation of these nanoparticles into a hydrogel facilitates their sustained release in time. Moreover, the formulation of this hydrogel containing PTX-loaded responsive nanoparticles and free TMZ was able to delay tumour recurrence in vivo after resection surgery. Therefore, our formulation represents a promising approach to develop combined local therapies against GBM using injectable hydrogels containing nanoparticles.

4. Ultimo, A., Orzaez, M., Santos-Martinez, M. J., Martínez-Mañez, R., Marcos, M. D., Sancenón, F., & Ruiz-Hernández, E. High-capacity mesoporous silica nanocarriers of siRNA for applications in retinal delivery. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* (2023) 24(3), 2753. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24032753>

Abstract: The main cause of subretinal neovascularisation in wet age-related macular degeneration (AMD) is an abnormal expression in the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) of the vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). Current approaches for the treatment of AMD present considerable issues that could be overcome by encapsulating anti-VEGF drugs in suitable nanocarriers, thus providing better penetration, higher retention times, and sustained release. In this work, the ability of large pore mesoporous silica nanoparticles (LP-MSNs) to transport and protect nucleic acid molecules is exploited to develop an innovative LP-MSN-based nanosystem for the topical administration of anti-VEGF siRNA molecules to RPE cells. siRNA is loaded into LP-MSN mesopores, while the external surface of the nanodevices is functionalised with polyethylenimine (PEI) chains that allow the controlled release of siRNA and promote endosomal escape to facilitate cytosolic delivery of the cargo. The successful results obtained for VEGF silencing in ARPE-19 RPE cells demonstrate that the designed nanodevice is suitable as an siRNA transporter.

5. Maher, R., Moreno-Borrillo, A., Jindal, D., Mai, B. T., Ruiz-Hernandez, E., & Harkin, A. Intranasal Polymeric Lipid-Based Nanocarriers for CNS Drug delivery. *Pharmaceutics* (2023) 15(3), 746. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15030746>

Abstract: Nanomedicine is currently focused on the design and development of nanocarriers that enhance drug delivery to the brain to address unmet clinical needs for treating

neuropsychiatric disorders and neurological diseases. Polymer and lipid-based drug carriers are advantageous for delivery to the central nervous system (CNS) due to their safety profiles, drug-loading capacity, and controlled-release properties. Polymer and lipid-based nanoparticles (NPs) are reported to penetrate the blood–brain barrier (BBB) and have been extensively assessed in in vitro and animal models of glioblastoma, epilepsy, and neurodegenerative disease. Since approval by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of intranasal esketamine for treatment of major depressive disorder, intranasal administration has emerged as an attractive route to bypass the BBB for drug delivery to the CNS. NPs can be specifically designed for intranasal administration by tailoring their size and coating with mucoadhesive agents or other moieties that promote transport across the nasal mucosa. In this review, unique characteristics of polymeric and lipid-based nanocarriers desirable for drug delivery to the brain are explored in addition to their potential for drug repurposing for the treatment of CNS disorders. Progress in intranasal drug delivery using polymeric and lipid-based nanostructures for the development of treatments of various neurological diseases are also described.

6. de la Torre, C., Coll, C., Ultimo, A., Sancenón, F., Martínez-Máñez, R., & Ruiz-Hernández, E. In Situ-Forming Gels Loaded with Stimuli-Responsive Gated Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Local Sustained Drug Delivery. *Pharmaceutics* (2023) 15(4), 1071. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15041071>

Abstract: A novel combination of in situ-forming hydrogels of hyaluronic acid with gated mesoporous materials was developed to design depots for local sustained release of chemotherapeutics. The depot consists of a hyaluronic-based gel loaded with redox-responsive mesoporous silica nanoparticles loaded with safranin O or doxorubicin and capped with polyethylene glycol chains containing a disulfide bond. The nanoparticles are able to deliver the payload in the presence of the reducing agent, glutathione (GSH), that promotes the cleavage of the disulfide bonds and the consequent pore opening and cargo delivery. Release studies and cellular assays demonstrated that the depot can successfully liberate the nanoparticles to the media and, subsequently, that the nanoparticles are internalized into the cells where the high concentration of GSH induces cargo delivery. When the nanoparticles were loaded with doxorubicin, a significant reduction in cell viability was observed. Our research opens the way to the development of new depots that enhance the local controlled release of chemotherapeutics by combining the tunable properties of hyaluronic gels with a wide range of gated materials.

7. Spitz S., Schobesberger, S., Brandauer K., Ertl P. (2023). Sensor-integrated brain-on-a-chip platforms: Improving the predictive validity in neurodegenerative research. *Bioengineering & Translational Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/btm2.10604>.

Abstract: Affecting millions of individuals worldwide, neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) pose a significant and growing health concern in people over the age of 60 years. Contributing to this trend are the steady increase in the aging population coupled with a persistent lack of disease-altering treatment strategies targeting NDDs. The absence of efficient therapeutics can be attributed to high failure rates in clinical trials and the ineptness of animal models in preceding preclinical studies. To that end, in recent years, significant research effort has been dedicated to the development of human cell-based preclinical disease models characterized by a higher degree of predictive validity. However, a key requirement of any in vitro model constitutes the precise knowledge and replication of the target tissues' (patho-)physiological

microenvironment. Herein, microphysiological systems have demonstrated superiority over conventional static 2D/3D in vitro cell culture systems, as they allow for the emulation and continuous monitoring of the onset, progression, and remission of disease-associated phenotypes. This review provides an overview of recent advances in the field of NDD research using organ-on-a-chip platforms. Specific focus is directed toward non-invasive sensing strategies encompassing electrical, electrochemical, and optical sensors. Additionally, promising on- and integrable off-chip sensing strategies targeting key analytes in NDDs will be presented and discussed in detail.

8. Jarić S., Schobesberger S., Velicki L., Milovančev A., Nikolić N., Ertl P., Bobrinetskiy I., Knežević N. Direct electrochemical reduction of graphene oxide thin film for aptamer-based selective and highly sensitive detection of matrix metalloproteinase 2. *Talanta* (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2024.126079>.

Abstract: Simple and low-cost biosensing solutions are suitable for point-of-care applications aiming to overcome the gap between scientific concepts and technological production. To compete with sensitivity and selectivity of golden standards, such as liquid chromatography, the functionalization of biosensors is continuously optimized to enhance the signal and improve their performance, often leading to complex chemical assay development. In this research, the efforts are made on optimizing the methodology for electrochemical reduction of graphene oxide to produce thin film-modified gold electrodes. Under the employed specific conditions, 20 cycles of cyclic voltammetry (CV) are shown to be optimal for superior electrical activation of graphene oxide into electrochemically reduced graphene oxide (ERGO). This platform is further used to develop a matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP-2) biosensor, where specific anti-MMP2 aptamers are utilized as a biorecognition element. MMP-2 is a protein which is typically overexpressed in tumor tissues, with important roles in tumor invasion, metastasis as well as in tumor angiogenesis. Based on impedimetric measurements, we were able to detect as low as 3.32 pg mL⁻¹ of MMP-2 in PBS with a dynamic range of 10 pg mL⁻¹ – 10 ng mL⁻¹. Further experiments with real blood samples revealed a promising potential of the developed sensor for direct measurement of MMP-2 in complex media. High specificity of detection is demonstrated – even to the closely related enzyme MMP-9. Finally, the potential of reuse was demonstrated by signal restoration after experimental detection of MMP-2.

9. Kudriavtseva A, Jarić S, Nekrasov N, Orlov AV, Gadjanski I, Bobrinetskiy I, Nikitin PI, Knežević N. Comparative Study of Field-Effect Transistors Based on Graphene Oxide and CVD Graphene in Highly Sensitive NT-proBNP Aptasensors. *Biosensors* (2024) 14, 215. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios14050215>.

Abstract: Graphene-based materials are actively being investigated as sensing elements for the detection of different analytes. Both graphene grown by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and graphene oxide (GO) produced by the modified Hummers' method are actively used in the development of biosensors. The production costs of CVD graphene- and GO-based sensors are similar; however, the question remains regarding the most efficient graphene-based material for the construction of point-of-care diagnostic devices. To this end, in this work, we compare CVD graphene aptasensors with the aptasensors based on reduced GO (rGO) for their capabilities in the detection of NT-proBNP, which serves as the gold standard biomarker for heart failure. Both types of aptasensors were developed using commercial gold interdigitated electrodes (IDEs) with either CVD graphene or GO formed on top as a channel of liquid-gated

field-effect transistor (FET), yielding GFET and rGO-FET sensors, respectively. The functional properties of the two types of aptasensors were compared. Both demonstrate good dynamic range from 10 fg/mL to 100 pg/mL. The limit of detection for NT-proBNP in artificial saliva was 100 fg/mL and 1 pg/mL for rGO-FET- and GFET-based aptasensors, respectively. While CVD GFET demonstrates less variations in parameters, higher sensitivity was demonstrated by the rGO-FET due to its higher roughness and larger bandgap. The demonstrated low cost and scalability of technology for both types of graphene-based aptasensors may be applicable for the development of different graphene-based biosensors for rapid, stable, on-site, and highly sensitive detection of diverse biochemical markers.

10. Mundžić M, Lazović J, Mladenović M, Pavlović A, Ultimo A, Gobbo O, Ruiz-Hernandez E, Santos-Martinez MJ, Knežević N.Ž. MRI-based sensing of pH-responsive content release from mesoporous silica nanoparticles. *Journal of Sol-Gel Science and Technology* (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10971-024-06422-9>.

Abstract: A proof of principle study toward developing a novel methodology which could be applicable for a non-invasive monitoring of the release of cargo molecules from therapeutic and diagnostic nanoparticles, as well as for possible monitoring of tissue pH variations. This was achieved by quantifying changes in longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) before and after the pH-responsive release of contrast agents, for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), from the pores of mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs). The pores were filled with the FDA-approved contrast agent Gadobutrol (GdB), and its retention inside the pores ensured by covalent attachment of β -cyclodextrin monoaldehyde to hydrazine-functionalized MSN, through acidification-cleavable hydrazone linkage. The release kinetics of GdB was measured by fluorescence spectroscopy which revealed that the release of the contrast agent was enhanced at pH 5.0 in comparison to the release at pH 6.0 and 7.4. Furthermore, the changes in T_1 , occurring in response to the enhanced release of GdB from the pores of MSN at weakly acidic conditions, were successfully demonstrated by MRI measurements. It is envisioned that this approach using contrast agent-loaded nanoparticles before the treatment with the drug-filled analogs, could be applied in the future for tracking the locations and efficacies of nanomedicines for therapeutic cargo delivery.

11. Mladenović, M., Jarić, S., Mundžić, M., Pavlović, A., Bobrinetskiy, I., Knežević, N.Ž. Biosensors for Cancer Biomarkers based on Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles, *Biosensors* (2024) 14(7), 326; <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios14070326>

Abstract: Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) exhibit highly beneficial characteristics for devising efficient biosensors for different analytes. Their unique properties, such as capabilities for stable covalent binding to recognition groups (e.g., antibodies or aptamers) and sensing surfaces, open a plethora of opportunities for biosensor construction. In addition, their structured porosity offers capabilities for entrapping signaling molecules (dyes or electroactive species), which could be released efficiently in response to a desired analyte for effective optical or electrochemical detection. This work offers an overview of recent research studies (in the last five years) that contain MSNs in their optical and electrochemical sensing platforms for the detection of cancer biomarkers, classified by cancer type. In addition, this study provides an overview of cancer biomarkers, as well as electrochemical and optical detection methods in general.

3. PREPRINT PUBLICATIONS

1. Kundacina, I., Schobesberger, S. Kittler, S., Thumfart, H., Spadiut, O., Ertl, P, Knezevic, N.Ž. Radonic, V., A Versatile Gold Leaf Immunosensor with a Novel Functionalization Strategy Based on Protein L-Modified Surface for Efficient Her2 Detection. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4740306> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4740306>

Abstract: Although various sensors specifically developed for target analytes are available, affordable biosensing solutions with broad applicability are limited. In this study, a cost-effective biosensor for detecting human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) was developed using custom-made gold leaf electrodes (GLEs). A novel strategy for antibody immobilization on a gold surface, mediated by protein L, was examined using commercial screen-printed gold electrodes and GLEs. This versatile immobilization strategy enables the application of the functionalized GLEs for the detection of antibodies and antigens. A self-assembled monolayer of 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA) on the gold surface, was used to immobilize protein L, further binding trastuzumab to detect HER2 using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The HER2 detection was examined in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and supplemented cell culture medium. The modified GLEs showed good specificity and high sensitivity of HER2 detection without any enrichment steps, achieving a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.02 ng mL⁻¹ in PBS and 0.03 ng mL⁻¹ in cell culture medium, making the proposed immunosensor a cost-effective and sensitive solution for detection in complex biological matrices.

2. Mundžić, M., Ultimo, A., Lazović, J., Mladenović M, Pavlović A, Gobbo O, Ruiz-Hernandez E, Santos-Martinez MJ, Knežević N.Ž. pH-responsive Nanosystems for Targeted Drug Delivery to Glioblastoma Multiforme and MRI-facilitated Monitoring of Content Release, 11 December 2023, PREPRINT (Version 1) available at Research Square [<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3709910/v1>]

Abstract: Despite the current state-of-the-art glioblastoma treatment options, a clear indication of therapeutic delivery and efficacy is still missing, especially in early therapy. Substantial advancements, particularly in the areas of image-guided and targeted therapy of the most aggressive type of brain cancer-Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), are needed to improve the quality of life and survival rates of patients. Herein we describe a proof of principle study toward developing a novel methodology for non-invasive monitoring of the release of cargo molecules from theranostic nanoparticles. This is achieved by quantifying changes in longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) before and after the pH-responsive release of contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), from the pores of GBM-targeted mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs). The pores of MSNs were loaded either with the anticancer drug paclitaxel (PTX) or FDA-approved contrast agent Gadobutrol, and their retention inside the pores was ensured by covalent attachment of β -cyclodextrin monoaldehyde to hydrazine-functionalized MSN, through acidification-cleavable hydrazone linkage. In vitro studies using a GBM cell line revealed that the developed nanoparticles effectively delivered their therapeutic cargo, leading to cell death, which was further enhanced with additional functionalization of MSNs with glioma-homing oligopeptide chlorotoxin (CHX). Furthermore, the changes in T_1 , occurring in response to the release of GdB from the pores of MSNs were successfully demonstrated by MRI measurements. These results are promising for the development of MRI-based methodology for monitoring and tracking the release of therapeutic content in tumor tissues. It is envisioned that this approach using contrast agent-loaded nanoparticles, before the treatment with the drug-filled analogues, could be applied in the future to provide increasingly personalized clinical management of cancer patients.

4. CONFERENCE PAPERS

NANOFACTS has also produced the following papers from contributions to international Conferences:

1. N. Ž. Knežević, N. Ilić, G. N. Kaluđerović. Functionalized Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Drug Delivery to Glioblastoma, Multiforme. 22nd IEEE International Conference on Nanotechnology (IEEE-NANO 2022): Book of Abstracts, 4-8 July 2022, Palma de Mallorca, Spain. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9928669>

Abstract: Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are covalently functionalized with Ir(III)-based complex and further characterized by nitrogen sorption, SEM, FTIR, EDS, TGA, DSC, DLS and zeta potential measurements. Controlled, pH-responsive delivery Ir(III)-complexes was noticed and demonstrated for efficient treatment of glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) cells upon exposure to acidification.

2. A. Ultimo, S. Ghosh, T. Frawley, MJ Santos-Martinez, O Piskareva, E. Ruiz-Hernández. Exosomes and stimuli-responsive mesoporous silica nanoparticles for a combined anti-tumour strategy. 7th International Conference on Multifunctional, Hybrid and Nanomaterials (HYMA 2022), 19–22 October 2022, Genoa, Italy.

Abstract: In recent years, the design and development of nanomaterials with a precise drug transport and delivery purpose has taken on considerable significance. Here are presented the results obtained in the development of a combination strategy applied to the treatment of two tumour models: neuroblastoma, the most common extracranial solid tumour that occurs in early childhood, representing around 8% of paediatric cancers; and glioblastoma multiforme, a brain tumour and one of the deadliest neoplasms with a median survival of 12-15 months. The proposed strategy involves the administration in two sequential steps of: 1) targeted cancer-derived exosomes loaded with tumour suppressor oligonucleotides, and 2) stimuli-responsive mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) loaded with doxorubicin, and incorporating targeting ligands and chitosan-based molecular gates able to temporarily cap the pores and further induce the cargo release in the lower pH of the tumour microenvironment. The bare and the chitosan-grafted MSNs have shown no effect on cells' viability, and demonstrated a good hemocompatibility. The assessment of the efficacy of the combined strategy has been performed in neuroblastoma and glioblastoma multiforme cell lines, both in 2D and 3D cultures. Targeted MSNs with a high payload of drug, administered after targeted tumour-inhibiting exosomes, could represent a powerful synergistic strategy to improve the efficacy of currently existing therapeutics.

3. A. Pavlović, M. Mladenović, M. Mundžić, Nanosensor for the detection of glutathione. 15th Scientific Conference Students encountering science – StES 2022, 17-19 November 2022, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina. <https://zenodo.org/records/7400809>

Abstract: Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are promising materials for bioanalyte detection and targeted drug delivery applications due to their characteristic properties, large

specific surface area and porosity, and the possibility of surface functionalization. The development of optimized and personalized diagnostic tools targeting glutathione (GSH), based on these nanomaterials for detection in the tumor environment, will provide real-time data on patients' cancer tissue.

4. T. Knežić, M. Djisalov, LAMP PRIMER DESIGN FOR MONITORING GENE EXPRESSION OF TUMOR MARKERS IN 3D CANCER CULTURES, 15th Scientific Conference Students encountering science – StES 2022, 17-19 November 2022, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina. <https://zenodo.org/records/7400865#.Y44K9nbMKUk>

Abstract: Cancer is one of the deadliest diseases, and its early detection and timely treatment are extremely important. The use of 3D cultures (spheroids) is the most relevant approach in cancer research because it mimics the in vivo environment of cells. Monitoring the tumor marker expression with different diagnostic methods is very important in determining specific therapy. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) is an innovative molecular tool that has a wide application, including the field of cancer diagnostics.

5. Nikola Knežević, Minja Mladenović, Mirjana Mundžić, Aleksandra Pavlović, Mila Djisalov, Teodora Knežić, & Ivana Gadjanski. (2023, February 9). Cyclodextrin-Capped Mesoporous Silica-Based Nanomaterials for pH-Responsive Targeted Theranostics of Glioblastoma Multiforme. International meet on pharmaceuticals and drug delivery systems (PHARMAMEET2023), Porto, Portugal. <https://zenodo.org/records/7665435>

Abstract: Purpose/Objectives: Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) exhibit highly beneficial features for devising efficient nanosystems for applications in targeted cancer theranostics. Our research focuses on developing multifunctionalized and multifunctional MSN-based nanotherapeutics. Materials/Methods: The surface of MSN is functionalized with suitable biomolecules for effective targeting of brain cancer (Glioblastoma multiforme, GBM). Further surface functionalization is performed to endow the materials with linkers that are cleavable in a weakly acidic environment. This attribute is desirable to enhance the specificity of drug delivery to cancer through favorable drug release in the weakly acidic environment of tumor tissues. The anticancer drug paclitaxel is loaded in the mesopores of MSN and its retention is ensured by the acidification-cleavable linkers. Results: The release kinetics of cargo molecules is monitored and the enhanced drug release in the weakly acidic environment is observed. Furthermore, MSNs containing Gadolinium-based contrast agents were developed for enabling GBM-targeted magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of tumor tissues. The toxicity of the materials and their cell uptake was demonstrated against GBM cells in vitro, in addition to the determination of their capabilities for tumor-targeted MRI. Conclusions: The research results evidence promising characteristics of the developed MSNs for applications in targeted treatment and magnetic resonance imaging of tumor tissues.

6. N. Ž. Knežević, M. Mundžić, M. Mladenović, A. Pavlović, A. Ultimo, O. L. Gobbo, E. Ruiz-Hernandez, M. Santos-Martinez. pH- and Redox-Responsive Cancer Nanotheranostics Based on Cyclodextrin-Capped Mesoporous Silica. 20th International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnologies, Abstract book, P97, July 4-7, 2023, Thessaloniki, Greece. <https://zenodo.org/records/8158522>.

Abstract: Versatile chemical modalities for multi-step surface functionalization of mesoporous silica nanoparticle (MSN) open a plethora of possibilities for devising nanosystems for applications in targeted cancer therapy and imaging. Herein, recent research efforts on the development of multifunctionalized MSN-based nanotherapeutics for targeted treatment and imaging of glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) are described. MSN's surface was functionalized with GBM-targeting biomolecules, while further surface functionalization was performed to endow the materials with linkers that are cleavable in the weakly acidic microenvironment of tumors or in the presence of tumor-overexpressed glutathione (GSH). The entrapment of cargo molecules (dyes, anticancer drugs or contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)) within MSN's pores was achieved by binding cyclodextrin analogues to the pH- or GSH-cleavable linkers on the MSN's surface. The release kinetics of cargo molecules was monitored by UV/Vis and fluorescence measurements, and an enhanced cargo release in the weakly acidic environment and upon exposure to GSH was observed. Furthermore, MSNs containing gadolinium-based contrast agents were evaluated for possible imaging of tumor tissue in MRI. Biological activity of MSNs was investigated using U87 (GBM) cell line, while their cellular uptake ability was evaluated by confocal microscopy and flow cytometry. The research results evidence the promising potential of the developed MSNs for their application as GBM- targeted theranostic nanoparticle.

7. Stefan Jarić, Silvia Schobesberger, Peter Ertl, Nikola Knežević, Ivan Bobrinetskiy. Electrochemical detection of MMP-2 using graphene based aptasensor” XXXV EUROSENSORS, 10-13 September 2023, Lecce, Italy, <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2024097057>

Abstract: A graphene-based electrochemical biosensor was developed for the detection of matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP-2) endopeptidase, whose expression can be significantly related to the occurrence, metastasis, and prognosis of cancer. A specific anti-MMP-2 aptamer was successfully immobilized on the surface of electrochemically reduced graphene oxide via a pyrene-based linker, enabling the specific capture of MMP-2. The sensor was able to detect 1 ng mL^{-1} , with an overall detection time of less than 20 min. Moreover, the aptamer-based biosensor showed good specificity toward different unspecific proteins.

8. Jarić, S., Bobrinetskiy I., Low-cost platform for determination of NTproBNP in saliva using graphene-based aptasensor. 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology, 12-15 May, 2024. Seville, Spain

Detection of trace concentrations of biomarkers can be essential if non-invasive analysis is employed, such as sampling of saliva, urine, or sweat. A significant early-stage heart failure biomarker N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP) can be found in saliva in concentrations of thousand times less than in blood plasma suggesting that non-invasive analysis require outstanding low detection limit. In this research, we propose a reduced graphene oxide-based FET device to develop a biosensor using specific anti-NT-proBNP aptamers for the detection of NT-proBNP in saliva. To address the need for low concentration detection in saliva, we included a correlation analysis of two FET parameters, Dirac point shift and transconductance variation to provide reliable biosensor performance. Namely, depending on the ionic strength of the solution, we found that correlation is significant (>0.8) for 0.01X PBS, while it is zero for 0.1X PBS. This can be associated to the long aptamer chain, consisted of 72 bases, that has significant effect on doping of rGO channel and such effect is screened by the ions of higher concentrations ($> 16 \text{ mM}$). The analysis shows that chemical interaction between target and receptor is

transformed into electrical signal, which is a result of either direct doping effect or charge mobility change. With such an approach, we observed a broad dynamic range of NT-proBNP concentrations in 0.01X PBS of $10^0 - 10^5$ fg mL⁻¹. Additionally, femtomolar detection of NT-proBNP is achieved in artificial saliva with limit of detection of 41 fg mL⁻¹.

9. Knežević, N., Jarić, S., Kundačina, I., Radonić, V., Bobrinetskiy, I. Novel cost-effective electrochemical systems for sensing cancer biomarkers, Rapid Communication, 8th International Conference on Bio-Sensing Technology, 12-15 May, Seville, Spain

Abstract: Development of point-of-care (POC) biosensors for detection of cancer biomarkers is a crucial topic for enabling early detection of cancer occurrence and monitoring its progression. Our results showcase cost-effective solutions for detection of human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) based on custom-made gold leaf electrodes (GLEs) and Matrix proteinase 2 (MMP2) detection based on graphene-functionalized commercial screen-printed gold electrodes. Overexpressed HER2 biomarker has been classified as both a prognostic and predictive biomarker for breast cancer while MMP-2 is a protein that is typically overexpressed in tumor tissues, with important roles in tumor invasion, metastasis as well as in tumor angiogenesis. Different novel strategies are employed for optimization of the surface functionalization with suitable proteins, antibodies, and aptamers to achieve highly sensitive and specific interaction with cancer biomarkers. Electrochemical characterization was performed using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and the potential of biomarker-sensing was examined in phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and in a cell culture medium. The proposed solution showed good specificity and high sensitivity of HER2 detection without any enrichment steps, achieving a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.02 ng/mL in PBS and 0.03 ng/mL in cell culture medium, making the proposed sensor a cost-effective and sensitive candidate for detection in complex biological matrices. In case of the MMP-2 sensor, based on impedimetric measurements, we could detect as low as 3.32 pg/mL of MMP-2 in PBS with a wide dynamic range of 1 pg/mL – 10 ng/mL. Besides high specificity, rGO-based aptasensor showed a potential for reuse due to demonstrated successful signal restoration after experimental detection of MMP-2. These novel cost-effective biosensing systems represent a promising step toward future application for POC detection of HER2 and MMP2 cancer biomarkers.

10. Knežević, N.Ž., Mundžić, M., Lazović, J., Ultimo, A., Mladenović, M., Pavlović, A., Gobbo, O.L., Ruiz-Hernandez, E., Santos-Martinez, M.J. Potential of MRI-based sensing of cargo release from mesoporous silica for tracking drug delivery capabilities. NanoSpain, June 04-07, 2024. Tarragona, Spain.

Abstract: Novel research results on application of multi-step surface functionalized mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) in targeted cancer therapy and MRI imaging are demonstrated. The external surface of MSN is functionalized with Chlorotoxin which targets the most aggressive type of brain cancer-Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM). Entrapping drugs (e.g. Paclitaxel) and the FDA-approved MRI contrast agent Gadobutrol within the pores is achieved through binding of cyclodextrin to the pore entrances through an acidification-cleavable hydrazone linkage. This further enables pH-responsive drug or contrast agent release from the MSNs. The tests on cancer cells reveal the capabilities of the prepared materials to deliver drugs and kill cancer cells. On the other hand, the tests involving MRI measurements revealed the capabilities of real time tracking of the release of contrast agents by MRI, which evidences the promising potential for the development of MRI-based methodology for monitoring and tracking the release of therapeutic content.

11. Jarić, S.; Schobesberger, S.; Ertl, P.; Knežević, N.Ž.; Bobrinetskiy, I. Electrochemical Detection of MMP-2 Using Graphene-Based Aptasensor. *Proceedings* 2024, 97, 57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2024097057>

Abstract: A graphene-based electrochemical biosensor was developed for the detection of matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP-2) endopeptidase, whose expression can be significantly related to the occurrence, metastasis, and prognosis of cancer. A specific anti-MMP-2 aptamer was successfully immobilized on the surface of electrochemically reduced graphene oxide via a pyrene-based linker, enabling the specific capture of MMP-2. The sensor was able to detect 1 ng mL^{-1} , with an overall detection time of less than 20 min. Moreover, the aptamer-based biosensor showed good specificity toward different unspecific proteins.

Article

One-Step Photochemical Immobilization of Aptamer on Graphene for Label-Free Detection of NT-proBNP

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Abstract: A novel photochemical technological route for one-step functionalization of a graphene surface with an azide-modified DNA aptamer for biomarkers is developed. The methodology is demonstrated for the functionalization of a DNA aptamer for an N-terminal B-type natriuretic peptide (NT-proBNP) heart failure biomarker on the surface of a graphene channel within a system based on a liquid-gated graphene field effect transistor (GFET). The limit of detection (LOD) of the aptamer-functionalized sensor is 0.01 pg/ml, with short response time (75 s) for clinically relevant concentrations of the cardiac biomarker, which could be of relevance for point-of-care (POC) applications. The novel methodology could be applicable for the development of different graphene-based biosensors for fast, stable, real-time, and highly sensitive detection of disease markers.

Keywords: graphene biosensor; heart failure; field-effect transistor; point-of-care diagnostic; aptamer; azide modification; photochemistry

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1. Introduction

B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) has an important role in regulating circulation by acting on blood vessels in response to wall stress. The biologically active BNP is being cleaved from proBNP upon its secretion, in a process that also produces a biologically inactive N-terminal proBNP [1]. Compared to BNP with a half-life of about 20 min, NT-proBNP poses a longer half-life of 1–2 h, providing more effective target for ventricular status diagnostics [2,3]. Thus, NT-proBNP is considered as a promising heart failure marker for point-of-care (POC) diagnostic applications. POC devices containing functionalized antibodies for NT-proBNP detection have been developed so far with electrochemical [4] or colorimetric [5] signaling. However, the use of antibodies is expensive, while rapid, accurate, and early diagnostics of heart disease remains challenging. Recently, a new aptamer with high affinity to NT-proBNP was discovered [6] and its efficient use in development of biosensors was demonstrated [7,8]. The use of aptamers as bioreceptors is a prospective method for the development of low-cost aptasensors [9,10], which can also be improved by photochemical modification of carbon lattice [11].

Conventional methods for aptamer immobilization are based on π-π stacking of pyrene-based linkers, which require multiple steps for receptor layer binding. In addition, due to the noncovalent nature of functionalization, these biosensors may suffer from instability and fast degradation of characteristics during multiple washings and measurements [9,12]. The use of photochemistry for direct attachment of bioreceptors to carbon nanomaterials is a promising technology for large-scale and reproducible fabrication of biosensors. Recently, we demonstrated the direct method of covalent functionalization of carbon nanotube transistors with proteins using phenyl azide photochemistry [13]. The

Article

Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for pH-Responsive Delivery of Iridium Metallotherapeutics and Treatment of Glioblastoma Multiforme

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Abstract: Using nanoparticles for controlled drug delivery to cancer, in response to its weakly acidic environment, represents a promising approach toward increasing the effectiveness and reducing the adverse effects of cancer therapy. Hence, the aim of this study is to construct novel mesoporous silica nanoparticle (MSN)-based acidification-responsive drug delivery systems for targeted cancer therapy. Herein, the surface of MSN is covalently functionalized with Ir(III)-based complex through a pH-cleavable hydrazone-based linker and characterized by nitrogen sorption, SEM, FTIR, EDX, TGA, DSC, DLS, and zeta potential measurements. Enhanced release of Ir(III)-complexes is evidenced by UV/VIS spectroscopy at the weakly acidic environments (pH 5 and pH 6) in comparison to the release at physiological conditions. The *in vitro* toxicity of the prepared materials is tested on healthy MRC-5 cells while their potential for the efficient treatment of glioblastoma multiforme is demonstrated on the U251 cell line.

Keywords: pH-responsive; drug delivery; cancer therapy; iridium complex; metallotherapeutics; mesoporous silica nanoparticles

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1. Introduction

Typical problem that occurs in cancer chemotherapy is that it targets all rapidly dividing cells, i.e., healthy cells as well as cancer cells. As a possible solution, research advances are being made toward developing cancer-targeting therapeutics that may be capable of delivering therapeutic cargo specifically to cancer tissues and in response to the specific environment of cancer [1]. These advanced therapeutics for targeted cancer treatment and imaging are seen as a promising approach toward increasing treatment selectivity and for enhancing its efficiency [2]. The application of nanoparticles for stimuli-responsive drug delivery is one of the most favored strategies [3]. Namely, due to the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect that is observed in cancer tissues [4], nanoparticles exhibit an innate ability for accumulation in cancer tissues. Furthermore, their structure may enable preservation of the therapeutic cargo and prevent its premature release before reaching the target site, where it may be delivered in a controlled manner [5]. One of the possible approaches for achieving targeted cancer therapy is through devising nanotherapeutics for delivering cargo drugs in response to a weakly acidic cancer microenvironment [6,7]. Therapy with cancer-targeting nanoparticles could effect in reducing side effects [8], minimizing multidrug resistance [9], and increased intracellular drug concentration [10]. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN), owing to their customizable features, represent a nanomaterial with promising potential for designing advanced cancer-targeting nanotherapeutics for effective controlled drug and gene delivery applications [11–13]. Thus, for construction of

OPEN

Nanocomposite formulation for a sustained release of free drug and drug-loaded responsive nanoparticles: an approach for a local therapy of glioblastoma multiforme

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Malignant gliomas are a type of primary brain tumour that originates in glial cells. Among them, glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is the most common and the most aggressive brain tumour in adults, classified as grade IV by the World Health Organization. The standard care for GBM, known as the Stupp protocol includes surgical resection followed by oral chemotherapy with temozolomide (TMZ). This treatment option provides a median survival prognosis of only 16–18 months to patients mainly due to tumour recurrence. Therefore, enhanced treatment options are urgently needed for this disease. Here we show the development, characterization, and *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation of a new composite material for local therapy of GBM post-surgery. We developed responsive nanoparticles that were loaded with paclitaxel (PTX), and that showed penetration in 3D spheroids and cell internalization. These nanoparticles were found to be cytotoxic in 2D (U-87 cells) and 3D (U-87 spheroids) models of GBM. The incorporation of these nanoparticles into a hydrogel facilitates their sustained release in time. Moreover, the formulation of this hydrogel containing PTX-loaded responsive nanoparticles and free TMZ was able to delay tumour recurrence *in vivo* after resection surgery. Therefore, our formulation represents a promising approach to develop combined local therapies against GBM using injectable hydrogels containing nanoparticles.

Abbreviations

GBM Glioblastoma multiforme
 TMZ Temozolomide
 PTX Paclitaxel
 MSN Mesoporous silica nanoparticles

For more than 20 years, the standard of care for patients diagnosed with glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) has remained unchanged. When the location and size of the tumour permit it, surgical resection is performed. Following this, the patient receives radiotherapy and oral chemotherapy with temozolomide (TMZ)¹. This chemotherapeutic drug is an alkylating agent that acts by inducing base mismatches and DNA breaks, which impact cell replication². Thus, this drug is very active during oncogenesis, and radiotherapy plays a synergistic effect damaging the DNA of cancer cells, leading them to death³. Although TMZ can cross the blood–brain barrier to exert its effect, the high dose required for systemic treatment could induce serious side effects⁴. Moreover,

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Article

High-Capacity Mesoporous Silica Nanocarriers of siRNA for Applications in Retinal Delivery

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Abstract: The main cause of subretinal neovascularisation in wet age-related macular degeneration (AMD) is an abnormal expression in the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) of the vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). Current approaches for the treatment of AMD present considerable issues that could be overcome by encapsulating anti-VEGF drugs in suitable nanocarriers, thus providing better penetration, higher retention times, and sustained release. In this work, the ability of large pore mesoporous silica nanoparticles (LP-MSN) to transport and protect nucleic acid molecules is exploited to develop an innovative LP-MSN-based nanosystem for the topical administration of anti-VEGF siRNA molecules to RPE cells. siRNA is loaded into LP-MSN mesopores, while the external surface of the nanodevices is functionalised with polyethylimine (PEI) chains that allow the controlled release of siRNA and promote endosomal escape to facilitate cytosolic delivery of the cargo. The successful results obtained for VEGF silencing in ARPE-19 RPE cells demonstrate that the designed nanodevice is suitable as an siRNA transporter.

Keywords: age related macular degeneration; large pore mesoporous silica nanoparticles; siRNA delivery; VEGF silencing

1. Introduction

Nowadays, retinal vein occlusion, ocular tumours and several retinal diseases are known as the most common causes of progressive and irreversible angiogenesis-related blindness, i.e., age-related macular degeneration (AMD), in aged people, diabetic retinopathy in adults and premature retinopathy in children [1–5]. In particular, AMD is a multifactorial disease with a complex pathophysiology that leads to a progressive loss of central vision due to damaged retinal pigment epithelium (RPE) and photoreceptors in the macula, the central area of the retina [6]. AMD is responsible for more than half of the cases of legal blindness in elderly people in developed countries. An increased prevalence of the disease has been foreseen as a result of population ageing and underlines the urgency for implementing eye care therapies [7–10]. In its late stages, the disease can evolve into dry or wet AMD, the latter being the one that provokes a more severe vision loss [6,9]. Wet AMD occurs in patients who develop subretinal choroidal neovascularisation (CNV), an abnormal growth of the choriocapillaris through the membrane that separates the RPE from the choroid, the external highly vascularised layer which supplies the retina's metabolic

Review

Intranasal Polymeric and Lipid-Based Nanocarriers for CNS Drug Delivery

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Abstract: Nanomedicine is currently focused on the design and development of nanocarriers that enhance drug delivery to the brain to address unmet clinical needs for treating neuropsychiatric disorders and neurological diseases. Polymer and lipid-based drug carriers are advantageous for delivery to the central nervous system (CNS) due to their safety profile, drug-loading capacity, and controlled-release properties. Polymer and lipid-based nanoparticles (NPs) are reported to penetrate the blood–brain barrier (BBB) and have been extensively assessed in *in vitro* and animal models of glioblastoma, epilepsy, and neurodegenerative disease. Since approval by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of intranasal esketamine for treatment of major depressive disorder, intranasal administration has emerged as an attractive route to bypass the BBB for drug delivery to the CNS. NPs can be specifically designed for intranasal administration by tailoring their size and coating with mucosubhesive agents or other moieties that promote transport across the nasal mucosa. In this review, unique characteristics of polymeric and lipid-based nanocarriers desirable for drug delivery to the brain are explored in addition to their potential for drug repurposing for the treatment of CNS disorders. Progress in intranasal drug delivery using polymeric and lipid-based nanostructures for the development of treatments of various neurological diseases are also described.

Keywords: central nervous system (CNS); blood–brain barrier (BBB); PLGA nanoparticle (NP); solid lipid NP (SLN); intranasal

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1. Introduction

Central nervous system (CNS) diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), epilepsy, brain cancers, and many neuropsychiatric disorders, continue to cause a significant health burden worldwide. However, in the last decade, only 10% of new drugs approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) are for the treatment of CNS disorders [1]. Although this is a major research field, there is a lack of understanding of the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms of many neurological diseases. This is problematic for drug development and as a result, many available treatments provide only symptomatic relief. Despite promising preclinical evidence, many drug candidates fail in clinical trials due to a lack of efficacy. As an example, this is true for gantenerumab, a human anti-amyloid β (A β) monoclonal antibody, which Roche recently announced did not meet the primary endpoints of phase III trials, as amyloid clearance was less than expected and cognitive scores were non-significant (NCT03443973). This, in part, is likely due to poor delivery of the drug to the brain, resulting in a lack of therapeutic effect.

Drug targeting to the brain is a challenge, largely due to the presence of the blood–brain barrier (BBB). This is a highly selective, semipermeable structure comprising many types of brain cells, predominantly vascular endothelial cells, astrocyte end-feet, pericytes, and

Article

In Situ-Forming Gels Loaded with Stimuli-Responsive Gated Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles for Local Sustained Drug Delivery

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Abstract: A novel combination of in situ-forming hydrogels of hyaluronic acid with gated mesoporous materials was developed to design depots for local sustained release of chemotherapeutics. The depot consists of a hyaluronic-based gel loaded with redox-responsive mesoporous silica nanoparticles loaded with safranin O or doxorubicin and capped with polyethylene glycol chains containing a disulfide bond. The nanoparticles are able to deliver the payload in the presence of the reducing agent, glutathione (GSH), that promotes the cleavage of the disulfide bonds and the consequent pore opening and cargo delivery. Release studies and cellular assays demonstrated that the depot can successfully liberate the nanoparticles to the media and, subsequently, that the nanoparticles are internalized into the cells where the high concentration of GSH induces cargo delivery. When the nanoparticles were loaded with doxorubicin, a significant reduction in cell viability was observed. Our research opens the way to the development of new depots that enhance the local controlled release of chemotherapeutics by combining the tunable properties of hyaluronic gels with a wide range of gated materials.

Keywords: mesoporous silica; drug delivery; molecular gates; in situ-forming gels

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the development of sustained and controlled drug release systems has gained increasing interest in the field of cancer treatment as a way to reduce side effects and to improve the availability of chemotherapeutics at the tumor site. In this scenario, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) are attractive drug nanocarriers due to their high surface area, large pore volume, and tunable pore size, as well as their high efficiency in loading active molecules irrespective of their hydrophobic nature or relatively large size. Despite the significant potential of silica nanomaterials for healthcare applications, concerns related to their biocompatibility still remain to be fully addressed [1,2]. It is today well established that MSNs' biocompatibility depends on their size, morphology, composition, surface functionalization, and administration route.

In terms of administration, in most studies nanocarriers are formulated as suspensions and injected. However, the incorporation of nanoparticles into other matrices can be of great interest for certain medical applications, such as for the development of local drug delivery systems for solid tumor treatment. For instance, Ranganath and colleagues developed a delivery system formed by an alginate gel matrix entrapping paclitaxel-loaded poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) microspheres [3]. The in vitro release studies showed how the gel delivered the drug sustainably for more than 60 days with a minimal initial

Sensor-integrated brain-on-a-chip platforms: Improving the predictive validity in neurodegenerative research

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952259**Abstract**

Affecting millions of individuals worldwide, neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) pose a significant and growing health concern in people over the age of 60 years. Contributing to this trend are the steady increase in the aging population coupled with a persistent lack of disease-altering treatment strategies targeting NDDs. The absence of efficient therapeutics can be attributed to high failure rates in clinical trials and the ineptness of animal models in preceding preclinical studies. To that end, in recent years, significant research effort has been dedicated to the development of human cell-based preclinical disease models characterized by a higher degree of predictive validity. However, a key requirement of any in vitro model constitutes the precise knowledge and replication of the target tissues' (patho-)physiological micro-environment. Herein, microphysiological systems have demonstrated superiority over conventional static 2D/3D in vitro cell culture systems, as they allow for the emulation and continuous monitoring of the onset, progression, and remission of disease-associated phenotypes. This review provides an overview of recent advances in the field of NDD research using organ-on-a-chip platforms. Specific focus is directed toward non-invasive sensing strategies encompassing electrical, electrochemical, and optical sensors. Additionally, promising on- and integrable off-chip sensing strategies targeting key analytes in NDDs will be presented and discussed in detail.

KEYWORDS

microfluidics, microphysiological systems, neurodegenerative diseases, non-invasive monitoring, organ-on-a-chip technology, sensors

Translational Impact Statement

Insufficient predictive validity of animal-based disease models has restricted the progress in clinical trials targeting neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs). While significant efforts have been made in the replication of intricate micro-tissue analogs in vitro using OoC technology, these models still fail to integrate non-invasive sensing strategies, a prerequisite to effective system

Abbreviations: AD, Alzheimer's disease; ALS, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; A β , amyloid β ; BBB, blood-brain barrier; CMOS, complementary metal-oxide semiconductor; EES, electrical cell-substrate impedance sensing; HD, Huntington's disease; HEP, hepatoma proliferation; iPSC, induced pluripotent stem cell; L α L, leaf of drosophila; MIA, multi-electrode array; NDD, neurodegenerative disease; OoC, organ-on-a-chip; PD, Parkinson's disease; ROS, reactive oxygen species; SPR, surface plasmon resonance; TEER, trans-epithelial/endothelial electrical resistance; α -syn, α -synuclein.

Sarah Spitz, Silvia Schobesberger, and Konstanze Brandauer contributed equally to this study.

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Direct electrochemical reduction of graphene oxide thin film for aptamer-based selective and highly sensitive detection of matrix metalloproteinase 2

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ABSTRACT

Simple and lowest biosensing solutions are suitable for point-of-care applications aiming to overcome the gap between scientific concepts and technological production. To compete with sensitivity and selectivity of golden standards, such as liquid chromatography, the functionalization of biosensors is continuously optimized to enhance the signal and improve their performance, often leading to complex chemical assay development. In this research, the efforts are made on optimizing the methodology for electrochemical reduction of graphene oxide to produce thin film-modified gold electrodes. Under the employed specific conditions, 20 cycles of cyclic voltammetry (CV) are shown to be optimal for superior electrical activation of graphene oxide into electrochemically reduced graphene oxide (ERGO). This platform is further used to develop a matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP-2) biosensor, where specific anti-MMP2 aptamers are utilized as a biorecognition element. MMP-2 is a protein which is typically overexpressed in tumor tissues, with important roles in tumor invasion, metastasis as well as in tumor angiogenesis. Based on impedimetric measurements, we were able to detect as low as 2.22 ng mL⁻¹ of MMP-2 in PBS with a dynamic range of 10 ng mL⁻¹–10 ng mL⁻¹. Further experiments with real blood samples revealed a promising potential of the developed sensor for direct measurement of MMP-2 in complex media. High specificity of detection is demonstrated – even to the closely related enzyme MMP-9. Finally, the potential of reuse was demonstrated by signal restoration after experimental detection of MMP-2.

1. Introduction

Matrix metalloproteinase (MMPs) are enzymes of a broad spectrum of physiological and pathological processes primarily in an extracellular matrix (ECM) [1]. Increased MMP activities are known to occur in localized abnormal physiological conditions, such as cancer, enhancing angiogenesis but having also pro- or anti-angiogenic effect in cancer tissue and making them angiomodulators [2]. Matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP-2) or 72 kDa type-IV gelatinase is a type of MMP known for the degradation of collagen. MMP-2 is significantly involved in many pathological processes, especially in carcinogenic-related diseases, for

example, in prostate carcinogenesis [3] or breast carcinogenesis [4]. Because MMP-2 is evidenced to be overexpressed due to many different diseases, it is not considered as a specific biomarker of a disease, but rather as a prognostic biomarker [5].

The critical point is its concentration found in human fluids from healthy and diseased individuals. Morgie et al. evaluated MMP-2 activity (activated MMP-2) in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer (PC) from plasma samples [6]. Namely, a control group of people had a mean concentration of 14.2 ng mL⁻¹, patients with benign prostate hyperplasia (BPH) had 15.4 ng mL⁻¹, while patients with PC had 24.2 ng mL⁻¹ (no metastasis) and 52.4 ng mL⁻¹ (with metastasis). For a comparison,

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Article

Comparative Study of Field-Effect Transistors Based on Graphene Oxide and CVD Graphene in Highly Sensitive NT-proBNP Aptasensors

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Abstract: Graphene-based materials are actively being investigated as sensing elements for the detection of different analytes. Both graphene grown by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and graphene oxide (GO) produced by the modified Hummers’ method are actively used in the development of biosensors. The production costs of CVD graphene- and GO-based sensors are similar; however, the question remains regarding the most efficient graphene-based material for the construction of point-of-care diagnostic devices. To this end, in this work, we compare CVD graphene aptasensors with the aptasensors based on reduced GO (rGO) for their capabilities in the detection of NT-proBNP, which serves as the gold standard biomarker for heart failure. Both types of aptasensors were developed using commercial gold interdigitated electrodes (IDEs) with either CVD graphene or GO formed on top as a channel of liquid-gated field-effect transistor (FET), yielding GFET and rGO-FET sensors, respectively. The functional properties of the two types of aptasensors were compared. Both demonstrate good dynamic range from 10 fg/ml to 100 pg/ml. The limit of detection for NT-proBNP in artificial saliva was 100 fg/ml and 1 pg/ml for rGO-FET- and GFET-based aptasensors, respectively. While CVD GFET demonstrates less variations in parameters, higher sensitivity was demonstrated by the rGO-FET due to its higher roughness and larger bandgap. The demonstrated low cost and scalability of technology for both types of graphene-based aptasensors may be applicable for the development of different graphene-based biosensors for rapid, stable, on-site, and highly sensitive detection of diverse biochemical markers.

Keywords: graphene; graphene oxide; heart failure; field-effect transistor; point-of-care diagnostic; aptamer

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1. Introduction

Carbon-based nanomaterials are actively exploited in the development of biosensors due to several unique properties, like their high stability, inertness, biocompatibility, high sensitivity, and relatively easy functionalization. Graphene and its derivatives possess high potential as materials for point-of-care (POC) diagnostics due to the well-developed scalable processes of graphene production, either based on chemical vapor deposition (CVD) roll-to-roll technology [1], or ink-based methods for graphene oxide (GO) deposition [2]. Even though the production costs for the CVD graphene and GO-based biosensors are similar, the properties and applications’ functionality differ between these two types of graphene-based biosensors. Namely, CVD graphene represents an almost ideal intact crystal with zero band gap [3], while GO is a semiconducting material that preserves a band gap even

MRI-based sensing of pH-responsive content release from mesoporous silica nanoparticles

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Abstract

A proof of principle study toward developing a novel methodology which could be applicable for a non-invasive monitoring of the release of cargo molecules from therapeutic and diagnostic nanoparticles, as well as for possible monitoring of tissue pH variations. This was achieved by quantifying changes in longitudinal relaxation time (T_1) before and after the pH-responsive release of contrast agents, for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), from the pores of mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs). The pores were filled with the FDA-approved contrast agent Gadobutrol (GdBr), and its retention inside the pores ensured by covalent attachment of β -cyclodextrin monoaldehyde to hydrazine-functionalized MSN, through acidification-cleavable hydrazone linkage. The release kinetics of GdBr was measured by fluorescence spectroscopy which revealed that the release of the contrast agent was enhanced at pH 5.0 in comparison to the release at pH 6.0 and 7.4. Furthermore, the changes in T_1 , occurring in response to the enhanced release of GdBr from the pores of MSN at weakly acidic conditions, were successfully demonstrated by MRI measurements. It is envisioned that this approach using contrast agent loaded nanoparticles before the treatment with the drug-filled analogs, could be applied in the future for tracking the locations and efficacies of nanomedicines for therapeutic cargo delivery.

Graphical Abstract

Pores of β -maleimidopropionic acid hydrazide (BMPH)-functionalized mercaptopropyl-functionalized mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MPMSNs) were loaded with the contrast agent Gadobutrol and capped with β -cyclodextrin monoaldehyde. In weakly acidic environment the release of contrast agents was induced, and the enhanced release of GdBr at pH 5.0 vs. pH 7.4 was evidenced by magnetic resonance imaging measurements.

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Review

Biosensors for Cancer Biomarkers Based on Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles

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Abstract: Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) exhibit highly beneficial characteristics for devising efficient biosensors for different analytes. Their unique properties, such as capabilities for stable covalent binding to recognition groups (e.g., antibodies or aptamers) and sensing surfaces, open a plethora of opportunities for biosensor construction. In addition, their structured porosity offers capabilities for entrapping signaling molecules (dyes or electroactive species), which could be released efficiently in response to a desired analyte for effective optical or electrochemical detection. This work offers an overview of recent research studies (in the last five years) that contain MSNs in their optical and electrochemical sensing platforms for the detection of cancer biomarkers, classified by cancer type. In addition, this study provides an overview of cancer biomarkers, as well as electrochemical and optical detection methods in general.

Keywords: MSNs; biosensors; cancer biomarkers; electrochemical detection; optical detection

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1. Introduction

Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) are a mesostructured porous network of silicon oxide produced through the hydrolytic sol–gel process involving the hydrolysis and condensation of silicon alkoxide precursors under acidic or basic conditions in the presence of a surfactant template [1]. The formation of mesoporous silica typically involves a silica–surfactant micelle templating process, in which condensation of the silicon alkoxide precursor takes place around the surfactant acting as a structure-directing agent [2]. In this manner, hexagonally ordered spherical particles are obtained. MSNs possess precisely controllable physicochemical characteristics, such as particle size, morphology, pore dimensions and volume, surface area, and surface properties [3]. Furthermore, facile surface modification offers the possibility of tailoring the chemical and physical properties of MSNs to achieve specific characteristics or functionalities [4]. The adaptability of MSNs in terms of size, shape, and composition has led to their widespread utilization across various fields [5–8].

Bioanalytical devices that integrate nanotechnology with biological recognition elements, along with physicochemical transducers to detect and quantify specific biological and chemical substances, are considered nanobiosensors [9]. A transducer is an element that enables the conversion of the target–bioreceptor interaction into a measurable signal. On the other hand, a bioreceptor is a molecule that can interact with a specific analyte and gives the biosensor its specificity [10]. Selectivity, sensitivity, and stability are some of the main characteristics to consider when developing biosensors [11].

Integrating nanomaterials (NMs) in diagnostics opens a potential for increased sensitivity, reduced processing times, and improved cost-effectiveness [12] due to favorable NM characteristics such as increased relative surface area, high surface-to-volume ratio,